

PAIC-SWAT v.1.0
for MS Windows

**System for management of complex
SWAT models**

User Manual

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Procesu analīzes un izpētes centrs

SUMMARY

This is a User Manual for the software PAICSWAT v.1.0. The software is developed for the management of the water quality modelling systems developed within SWAT2009. Software functionality includes visualisation and postprocessing of the calculation results, analysis versus observation data series, changing coefficients and performing calculations. The software is aimed as a decision support tool for the SWAT users.

Manual is written English, it contains 36 pages, 35 figures, 5 tables and 4 references.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The software PAIC SWAT v.1.0 is a MS Windows application for the management of the water quality modelling systems developed within SWAT2009, Neitsch et al (2011). Software functionality includes visualisation and post-processing of the SWAT calculation results, analysis of modeled versus observed data series, changing coefficients and performing calculations.

The software is aimed as a decision support tool for the SWAT users. The development of PAIC SWAT software was performed during the project ELLE & PAIC (2012a). This documents is based on the examples of the water quality modelling system for Lithuania described in ELLE & PAIC (2012b)

The chapters of this User manual include:

1. The description of the file system comprising the SWAT water quality model for the use with PAIC SWAT in Chapter 2.
2. The description of the PAIC-SWAT user interface in Chapter 3 including the functionality of the electronic map (Section 3.1), basic visualisation of time graphs (Section 3.2) and the functionality of the pull-down menu system (Section 3.3).
3. The use of PAIC SWAT for statistical comparison with the observations is described in Chapter 4.
4. The use of the PAIC SWAT for management of the SWAT model parameters and performing calculations is described in Chapter 5.

PAIC SWAT v.1.0 is written in Borland Delphi 7, Borland (2002).

2. FILE SYSTEM

The application of the PAIC SWAT requires that the SWAT water quality model (or complex model system) is established. In this manual we use an example from the water quality modelling system (WQMS) of Lithuania described in ELLE & PAIC (2002b) for the illustration of PAIC SWAT usage. See the generalised file and folder structure of WQMS in Figure 1.

The PAIC SWAT has the following components and requirements to the existence, location and availability of files:

1. Program executable *paicswat.exe* in the root folder of WQMS.
2. File *paicswat.ini* – an ASCII file describing the WQMS structure. PAIC SWAT reads this initialisation file when starting. It includes the following information (Table 1):
 - a. Global time slots [*Globals*] – calculation period, calibration period and validation period.
 - b. Location of the files of geospatial information [*Maps*] – river nodes *NodesSHPFile*, river lines *RiverSHPFile*, river basins and their connections *BasinSHPFile*, connectivity matrix between the SWAT setups *ConnectionFile*, and transboundary river basins *transboundaryBasinFile*.
 - c. Location of the hydrometric and water quality observation data files [*Observations*] – *Qobs* and *WQobs*.

Table 1. Contents of the PAIC SWAT initialisation file *paicswat.ini*.

```

[Globals]
; general period under consideration
BasePeriod=2000-2010
; base calibration and validation periods
CalibPeriod=2000-2005
ValidPeriod=2006-2010
[Maps]
NodesSHPFile=Data/nodes.shp
NodeIDField=node_id
RiversSHPFile=Data/upes.shp
riverIDField=Catch
riverFlowFromField=Cach_F
riverFlowToField=Cach_T
riverNodeFromField=Node_F
riverNodeToField=Node_T
BasinsSHPFile=Data/Baseinu_global_saistibas_simplify.shp
SubbasinField=Subbasin
SetupNameField=Setup_name
gridCodeField=GRIDCODE
catchmentIDField=cach_id
catchmentFlowToField=cachto
catchmentAreakm2Field=area
ConnectionFile=Tabulas/Baseini_konekcijas.txt
transboundaryBasinFile=Data/Transboundary.shp
transboundaryAddAreafield=ADD_AREA
[Observations]
Qobs=Observations\Qobs.txt
WQobs=Observations\WQobs.txt
[Project.1]
...
[Project.2]
Name=Bartuva_Bartuva_Skuodas
Directory=Bartuva\Bartuva_Skuodas\Scenarios\Default
DefaultCase=TxtInOut
QReachNr=1
QStationID=5
QCalib=2000-2005
QValid=2006-2010
WQReachNr=8,1
WQStationID=78,79
WQCalib=2000-2005,2000-2005
WQValid=2006-2010,2006-2010
...
[Project.N]
Name=Nemunelis_Nemunelis_LT
...

```

- d. The description of the particular SWAT setups in the information blocks *[Project1]*, *[Project2]* , ... , *[ProjectN]*. Each project information block contains:
 - i. Setup *[Name]*, *[Directory]* of SWAT results and the folder name for *[DefaultCase]* calculations.
 - ii. Description of the link between the SWAT setup, hydrometric station and selected calibration/validation periods *[QReachNr]*, *[QStationID]*, *[QCalib]* and *[Qvalid]*.
 - iii. Description of the link between the SWAT setup, water quality observation station and selected calibration/validation periods *[WQReachNr]*, *[WQStationID]*, *[WQCalib]* and *[WQvalid]*.
3. Geospatial information files (folder *Data*) should contain the following information:
 - a. *Baseinu_global_saistibas_simplify.shp* is a shape file containing the information on the subbasins and connections between subbasins globally.
 - b. Shape file *nodes.shp* contains points and information about the river nodes.
 - c. Shape file *transboundary.shp* contains information about transboundary subbasins and their area.
 - d. Shape file *upes.shp* contains the river lines.
 4. Additional information should be present in folders *Tabulas* (file *Baseini_konekcijas.txt* contains information of connections between SWAT setups) and *Observations* (ASCII files *QObs.sta* and *QObs.txt* are, respectively, discharge observation data file and station list, but ASCII files *WQObs.sta* and *WQObs.txt* are, respectively, water quality observation data file and station list).
 5. Folders of particular SWAT setups (including SWAT calculation results) according to the list of projects in *paicswat.ini*.

The use of PAIC SWAT assumes application of *SWAT2009 rev.477* for the SWAT modelling. The running SWAT from PAIC SWAT requires a presence of SWAT executable [re]named *SWAT2009_PAIC.exe* in the root folder.

3. USER INTERFACE

The screenshot of the PAIC SWAT work session is shown in Fig. 2. The user interface is organised in the following functional blocks:

Figure 2. Screenshot of the PAIC SWAT with main functional blocks.

1. An interactive electronic 2D map in the upper left part of the screen and the control elements for the management of its contents are described in Section 3.1.
2. The graphical panel for visualisation of 1D graphs in the lower left part of the screen. The formatting of the 1D graph can be done via controls in the right middle panel, while the contents of the 1D graph panel are selected in the lower right multitab panel. Functionality of the 1D graph visualisation is described in Section 3.2.
3. Functionality of the pull down command menu is described in Section 3.3.
4. Two upper panels of the upper right part of the screen are aimed for (1) the selection of the results to be loaded in the software, see description in Section 3.1 and for the calculation/visualisation of the statistical integrals (Chapter 4).

3.1. Electronic map

The interactive electronic map of PAIC SWAT (Fig. 3) is located in the upper left part of the screen (Fig. 2). The elements of the working session may be shown in the electronic map: background map, objects of SWAT model setup – subbasins and reaches, discharge and water quality observation stations, arbitrary shape files. The composition of the map elements and the visualisation of these elements may be formatted by user, see details further in this Section.

Figure 3. The electronic 2D map of PAIC SWAT and its management panel.

The electronic map is separated from the 1D graph area below it by the red separator line. The ratio between the two screen blocks may be changed by dragging the mouse while holding its left button.

The electronic map can be switched on/off by the pull-down menu selection *View*→*Watershed overview*.

The following functionality is available in the electronic map:

1. **Zoom-in** by moving the mouse, holding its left button.
2. **Zoom-previous** by right-mouse-click.
3. **Zoom-out** by Ctrl+right-mouse-click.
4. **Zoom-default** by Shift+right-mouse-click.
5. **Scroll** by moving the mouse, holding its left button and Shift key.
6. The elements (subbasins of the SWAT setup, reaches of the subbasins, discharge and or water quality observation stations) of the visualisation may be **selected** by the left-mouse-click on the object. The selection of the objects cause the following actions:
 - 6.1. The information on the subbasin is displayed in the information window of the electronic map control panel if the subbasin or reach is selected. Information includes (1) the subbasin name and number in particular SWAT setup, (2) the area of subbasin itself A and the total catchment area at its outflow node $TOTA$ ($A=TOTA$ for upstream subbasins), (3) the names of the discharge (Q) and water quality (WQ) stations in the subbasin.
 - 6.2. The selected parameters or results (see Section 3.2 and Chapter 4) of the SWAT model relevant to the selected reach, subbasin or observation station are re-visualised in the 1D graph window.
 - 6.3. The items in the 1D graph content selection panel (see Section 3.2 and Chapter 4) are autofocused: (1) to the *.rte and *.sub files which correspond to the selected subbasin and reach in sub-tabs *RCH* and *SUB* of *Model* tab, (2) to the selected discharge station in the *Q* tab and (3) to the selected water quality station in the *WQ* tab.
7. Several objects may be selected at once by the sequential left-mouse-clicks, holding the Ctrl key.
8. The right-mouse-click activates the pop-up menu, if any of the active elements is selected. If the reach or subbasin is selected then the menu selection *Load setup* invokes the dialogue for loading of SWAT setup (Fig. 4) which is autofocused to the setup which includes the selected reach or subbasin. After loading of the particular setup in PAIC SWAT it is highlighted in the electronic map – see Fig. 3 with highlighted setup Šventoji-Širvinta.

The control panel of the 2D electronic map (to the right from the map, see Fig. 3) includes the following items and allow the following functionality:

1. The checkboxes *Subbasins*, *Reaches*, *Q observations*, *WQ observations* determine the display of the basic elements in the electronic map.

Figure 4. Dialogue window for the loading of particular SWAT setup.

Figure 5. 1D graph parameters window for handling visualisation of shape files.

2. The functional block *SHP files* is aimed for the adding and visualisation of the arbitrary layers of shape files in the electronic map (example in Fig. 3 includes the visualisation of the point source shape file in the electronic map).

- a. The checkboxes in the list of loaded shape files and the buttons *All* and *None* determine which shape files will be visualised.
- b. The button *Settings* invokes the *1D parameters* dialogue window for the management of *shp* files, see Fig. 5.
- c. The left part of the 1D parameter window (Fig. 5) contains a list of the shape files. Initially it is empty. User may add a new item to the list by right mouse click and selection *Add* from the pop-up menu.

Figure 6. Dialogue window for formatting the visualisation of the shape files (points).

- d. Button \rightarrow activates a dialogue (Figs. 6-8) for the design of the visualisation of the particular shape file.
 - i. Button *Select* activates the file selection dialogue for loading the shape file. Field *Layer type* is detected and filled automatically. An example in Fig. 6 is given for the formatting of the visualisation of the point source shape file (*Layer type Point*), Fig. 7 for the lines (*Layer type ArcM*), and Fig. 8 for the polygons (*Layer type Polygon*).
 - ii. Radiobuttons *Single symbol*, *Graduated* and *Category* determines whether all objects of shape file will be visualised identically (*Single symbol*), distinguished by category (*Category*) or

distinguished by gradual color palette according to values of the selected attribute (*Graduated*).

- iii. If the shape file includes points (Fig. 6), then the functional block *Marker* is activated. User may specify marker type, *Size*, *Fill color* and *Border color*. If the shape file includes lines (Fig. 7), then the functional block *Lines* is activated. User may select line *Color* and width. If the shape file includes polygon (Fig. 8), then the functional block *Polygon* is activated. User may select fill pattern and *Color*, as well as determine, whether to *Draw outline* of the polygon and select the respective line *Color* and width.

Figure 7. Dialogue window for formatting the visualisation of the shape files (lines).

- iv. If the *Graduated* or *Category* display of the shape file objects is selected then user may specify (Fig. 6-8) (1) *Field* (attribute) which is used for categorisation of the visualisation, (2) *Min value* and *Max value* of the attribute – these values can also be calculated automatically pressing the button *Find Min/Max* and (3) the number of categorisation *Steps* between *Min value* and *Max value*.
- v. The colour *Palette* for the categorising the shape file objects can be selected by pressing the respective button. It invokes the *Palette editor* (Fig. 9) which contains the following possibilities. The actual palette is displayed in the upper line and in the cells at the left side of the palette editor. Each cell contains colour number and sample. The mouse double-click on the colour sample activates the

colour selection dialogue. User may specify the *Palette entry count* in a selection field, and *Reverse* the colour sequence in the palette. All available palettes are displayed in the block *Predefined palettes*. The actual palette may be added to this list by button *Add to default list*. The palette from the list may be selected (actualised) by a mouse double-click. User may *Generate palette* in the respective functional block. The first and the last colour in the new palette may be selected by buttons *Select color 1* and *Select color 2*. The generation of the palette is activated by buttons *Generate RGB* or *Generate HSL*. User may *Save / Load* the actual palette in / from the *.cop files by respective buttons. User may *Save default / Load default* groups of the predefined palettes in / from the *.pls files by respective buttons.

Figure 8. Dialogue window for formatting the visualisation of the shape files (polygons).

- e. The line thickness and the name of the object from the shape file may be added in the fields next to \rightarrow button, Fig. 5. Buttons *L* and *S* are aimed for the loading and saving of the visualisation settings (as defined according to p.2d above) of the shape files.

- f. Functional block *Legend* (lower left corner of the 1D graph window, Fig. 5) allows to determine whether *Legend visible*, and set its *Font* and position.

Figure 9. *Palette editor* dialogue window.

- g. The right panel of the 1D graph window (Fig. 5) contains the settings controlling the zoom properties of the electronic map. Checkbox *Modify zoom* (in *off* position) suppresses automatic rescaling of the horizontal and vertical zoom of the electronic map after changing the number of shape objects. Checkbox *Zoom to all* determines that automatic zoom will account also the invisible shape file objects (i.e. those with checkboxes *off* in the control panel of the electronic map). Checkbox *X scale -> Auto* determines automatic calculation of the horizontal zoom (*on*). If the checkbox is *off*, then user may enter the horizontal zoom interval in the fields *Min*, *Max*. Checkbox *Y scale -> Auto* determines automatic calculation of the zoom for the vertical direction (*on*). If the checkbox is *off*, then user must enter the vertical zoom range in the respective fields.
- h. User may *Load* and *Save* all 1D graph settings in **.srb* files by respective buttons (Fig. 5).
3. The functional block *Server* (Fig. 3) is aimed for the management of connection to the external map server. The server URL must be entered in the respective field. The on-line requests from the server are initiated / finalised by the buttons *Open server* / *Close server*. The list of on-line map layers is provided in the information field. User may select (by left mouse click) the background map from this list; thus, example in Fig. 2 uses the areal photographic layer of map server www.maps.lt. The projection of the electronic map has to be provided with the

information request from the external server. The electronic map for the Lithuanian WQMS is drawn in EPGS:3346 (or LKS92) projection, see www.spatialreference.org.

4. The lower part of the control panel of the electronic map contains the information on the subbasin selected in the electronic map: (1) the subbasin name and number in particular SWAT setup, (2) the area of subbasin itself A and the total catchment area at its outflow node $TOTA$ ($A=TOTA$ for upstream subbasins), (3) the names of the discharge (Q) and water quality (WQ) stations in the subbasin (if any).

3.2. 1D graphs

The graphical window for the time graphs of either observations or SWAT model outputs is located in the lower left part of the PAIC SWAT user interface, see Fig. 2. It occupies the entire right part of the screen if the electronic map is suspended by menu selection *View*→*Watershed overview*, see Fig. 10. The visualisation of the observations is possible if only observation data are loaded – this typically occurs at the startup of program if only the *paicswat.ini* file contains a path to the valid discharge and/or water quality observation files, see Chapter 2. The visualisation of the SWAT model output data is possible if the particular model setup is loaded. It can be done either from the pop-up menu in the electronic map (Section 3.1) or from the pull-down menu by *File*→*Load case*.

Figure 10. 1D time graph window.

The time graphs of the selected parameters (see below and Chapter 4 on parameter selection) are shown in the graphical area. Time is shown along the horizontal axis, whilst the parameter values along the vertical axes – multi-axing is possible depending on the graph contents. The standard PAIC SWAT zoom functionality (see Section 3.1) is available in the graphical area.

Two functional blocks are aimed for the control of appearance and contents of the time graphs: (1) the *Visualisation settings* for formatting of 1D graph (see also Fig. 11) and (2) the selection of the contents of the 1D graph (see also Figs. 13-15).

Figure 11. Control panel *Visualisation settings*.

The *Visualisation settings* block (Fig. 11) contains the following functionality:

1. The block of checkboxes is a list of parameters (observations or model parameters) which are selected for visualisation. The checkboxes determine the graphs which will be shown in the graphical area. Buttons *All* and *None* switch on/off all checkboxes of the upper group.

Figure 12. Dialogue for formatting the 1D graph visualisation.

2. Button *Settings* activates the *1D graph parameters* dialogue (Fig. 12) for the formatting of the 1D graph visualisation.

2.1. The list of 1D graphs is shown in the left panel of the dialogue window. Button \rightarrow activates a *Line settings* dialogue (Fig. 13) for the design of the particular curve. The line thickness and legend may be specified in the *1D graph parameters* dialogue. Button *Modify all* activates the *Line settings* dialogue (p. 2.2) for the simultaneous modification of all 1D lines.

Figure 13. Dialogue for curve visualisation formatting *Line settings*.

2.2. The following options are available in the *Line settings* dialogue (Fig. 13).

2.2.1. The *Style* of the graph may be chosen between *Points*, *Line*, *Points and line* and *Bars*. User may select line *Color* and width in the functional block *Line*. If the 1D graph style includes points, then the functional block *Marker* is activated. User may specify marker type, *Size*, *Fill color* and *Border color*.

2.2.2. The data *Interpolation* method may be chosen as *Linear splines* or *Cubic splines*. The *Approximation* line may be added to the 1D graph. User may select the approximation method in the group of radio buttons *Kind* (*Linear*, *Quadratic*, *Cubic*, *Logarithmic*, *Exponential* and *Power* functions are available), and specify the *Color* and width of the *Approximation line*.

- 2.2.3. If a bar diagram is chosen for the visualisation, then user may select *Bar color*, fill pattern, and *Specified bar width*.
- 2.2.4. If the approximation is enabled then user may add the (*Moving average*) confidence interval to the approximation line. The selections are *Std. deviation* (user must specify the width of confidence interval - *Deviation*) or *Moving average* (user must specify the *Charact. Time interval* for averaging).
- 2.3. Functional block *Legend* in lower left part of 1D graph dialogue (Fig. 12) allows to determine whether *Legend visible*, and set its *Font* and position.
- 2.4. Checkbox *Modify zoom* (in *off* position) suppresses automatic rescaling of the horizontal and vertical zoom after changing the number of 1D graphs (by checkboxes in the control panel, Fig. 12).
- 2.5. Checkbox *Zoom to all* determines that automatic zoom will account also the invisible 1D graphs (i.e. graphs with checkboxes – off).
- 2.6. Checkbox *X scale* → *Auto* determines automatic calculation of the time interval of the graph (*on*). If the checkbox is *off*, then user may enter the time interval in the fields *Min*, *Max*.
- 2.7. Checkbox *Y scale* → *Auto* determines automatic calculation of the parameter intervals for the vertical axes (*on*). If the checkbox is *off*, then user must enter the parameter range in the grid columns *Min*, *Max*. Checkbox *Auto Tick* determines automatic tickmarks for the vertical axes (*on*). If the checkbox is *off*, then user must enter the parameter intervals between tickmarks in the grid column *Step*.
3. The checkboxes in the upper part of the *Visualisation settings* block (Fig. 11) determine the following postprocessing of the data before visualisation:
- 3.1. Checkbox *Concentrations* determine whether the water quality parameters will be displayed as mass fluxes (*off*, typically in kg/day) or as concentrations of substances (*on*, typically in mg/l).
- 3.2. Checkbox *Monthly value* determine whether all available data will be displayed in the 1D graph (*off*) or the monthly average values will be calculated and displayed (*on*).
- 3.3. Checkbox *Normalise by area* converts the discharge units of modelled reach level flows from m³/s to mm/day and divides any other reach level outputs (typically – the fluxes of substances) by the subbasin area.

The lower right part of the PAIC SWAT user interface is occupied by the selection of the observation or model output parameters for the visualisation. This control panel contains the following tabs (see Figs. 2, 14-17):

1. *Q* and *WQ* tabs (Fig. 14) are aimed for the selection of the observation results of, respectively, hydrometric and water quality stations. The lower part of these tabs contains an alphabetic list of all available stations (autofocused according to the SWAT subbasin selected in the electronic map if it contains an observation station). The upper part of *Q* and *WQ* tabs contains the lists of checkboxes corresponding to the observed parameters. Status of checkboxes determine whether particular parameter will be added to the checkbox list in the *Visualisation settings* panel.

Figure 14. *Q* and *WQ* tabs of the control panel for selection of 1D graphs.

2. *Model* multitablet (Figs. 15-16) is aimed for the selection of the SWAT model results. The lower part of all tabs of *Model* multitablet contains the lists of checkboxes corresponding to the available model output parameters. Status of checkboxes determine whether particular parameter will be added to the checkbox list in the *Visualisation settings* panel. The upper parts of the tabs differ:

Figure 15. *HRU* and *RCH* tabs of the *Model* tab of the control panel for selection of 1D graphs.

- a. *HRU* tab (Fig. 15 left) is aimed for the selection of the hydrological response unit level outputs. It contains the list of combinations of (land use) / (soil type) determining the HRUs of particular subbasin.
- b. *RCH* tab (Fig. 15 right) is aimed for the selection of the reach level outputs of SWAT model. It contains the list of *.*rte* files (i.e. reaches of subbasins) of the loaded setup. The list is autofocused to the reach / subbasin selected (if any) in the electronic map.
- c. *SUB* tab (Fig. 16 left) is aimed for the selection of the subbasin level outputs of SWAT model. It contains the list of *.*sub* files (i.e. subbasins) of the loaded setup. The list is autofocused to the subbasin selected (if any) in the electronic map.

- d. *RES* tab (Fig. 16 right) is aimed for the selection of the reservoir level outputs of SWAT model. It contains the list of *.res files (i.e. reservoirs) of the loaded setup.

Figure 16. *SUB* and *RES* tabs of the *Model* tab of the control panel for selection of 1D graphs.

3. *Calibration* tab (Fig. 17) is aimed for the selection of both the observations and the SWAT model results typically used for calibration. The left part of the tab (*Variables*) contains a list of radiobuttons of parameters for which the comparison of modeled and observed values are possible. The right part of the tab (*Q_Stations* and *WQ_Stations*) contains a list of radio buttons corresponding to the observation stations available in the loaded setup. The switching on of radiobuttons ensures (1) the visualisation of the selected parameters at selected places and (2) switching *On* the respective checkboxes in the *Model*, *Q* and *WQ* tabs. *Calibration* tab contains also a button *Calibration statistics* which is described in Chapter 4.

Figure 17. *Calibration* tab of the control panel for selection of 1D graphs.

3.3. Menu system

The pull-down menu system of PAIC SWAT v.1.0 is as follows:

1. *File* menu (Fig. 18 left) is aimed for file operations:
 - 1.1. *Load case* invokes a *Select Case* dialogue (Fig. 4) for loading one of the SWAT setups of the SWAT WQMS defined in *paicswat.ini*. This operation is alternative of the *Load case* from the pop-up menu of the electronic map. The status of the checkboxes in the result selection panel *Load settings* (Figs. 2 and 19) determines whether the hydrological response unit level results (checkbox *HRU*, applicable only if HRU level outputs are calculated by SWAT), reach results (*RCH*), subbasin results (*SUB*), soil results (*SOL*, applicable only if HRU level outputs are calculated by SWAT) and/or reservoir results (*RSV*) will be loaded. The aggregation of the HRU level results is possible over all subbasins of the setup (checkbox *Subbasin*), as well as over the *LandUse* and/or *Soil* type of HRUs. This aggregation affects both the results and the functionality of the SWAT parameter editor (Chapter 5).

Figure 18. *File* and *Edit* pull-down menus of PAIC SWAT.

Figure 19. *Load settings* panel.

- 1.2. *Load comparison case* invokes a *Select Case* dialogue (Fig. 20) for loading of another (different from default) set of calculation results for the same SWAT setup. The default folder of the SWAT results of the particular setups is specified in *paicswat.ini* file (*TxtInOut* in our example). Loading of comparison case is affected by the *Load settings* (Fig. 19). It causes appearance of the *Model2* multiten (see Fig. 21) in the control panel for the selection of calculation results for the visualisation. *Model2* multiten is equivalent to *Model* multiten (see description in Section 3.2); thus, two calculation cases of the same setup may be visualised and compared in 1D graphs.

1.3. *Load from directory* invokes a folder selection dialogue for loading of SWAT setup which is independent of the modelling system defined in *paicswat.ini*.

1.4. *Load observation file* loads the **.txt* file (should be selected in the file selection dialogue) and **.sta* file of any external observations (default set of observation data files includes discharge and water quality observations). Loading of additional observation file causes appearance of an additional tab (see Fig. 22) in the control panel for the selection of the visualisation contents. The name of the tab corresponds to the filename of the observation data.

Figure 20. *Select case* dialogue for loading of comparison case.

Figure 21. Appearance of the control panel for selection of visualisation elements after loading of comparison case.

Figure 22. Appearance of the control panel for selection of visualisation elements after loading of additional observation (weather) data.

1.5. *Clear loaded observations* discards all observations loaded by menu selection *Load observation file* and removes the respective additional tabs from the control panel for the selection of the visualisation contents.

1.6. *Reload Ini file* loads *paicswat.ini* file from the root folder.

2. *Edit* menu (Fig. 18 right) is aimed for copying the graphical image of 1D time graph window (*Copy picture*), numerical values of these time graphs (*Copy data*) and graphical image of the electronic map (*Copy map*) to the *Windows Clipboard*.
3. *Actions* menu (Fig. 23 left) is aimed for advanced operations related to the SWAT model setups.

Figure 23. *Actions* and *View* pull-down menus of PAIC SWAT.

- 3.1. *Edit SWAT variables* invokes the *Show/Edit SWAT variables* window for management of SWAT setup and performing SWAT model runs. The functionality of this window is described in Chapter 5.
- 3.2. *Basin statistics* opens a text window (Table 2) for the output of the basic catchment statistics by land use and soils for the loaded SWAT setup.

Table 2. Contents of the *Basin statistics* window.

Area,km2	915.21
P, mm/year	704
-----AREA BY LANDUSE-----	
AGRC	42.9%
AGRR	0.0%
APPL	0.1%
BARL	1.8%
....	
WWHT	3.8%
-----AREA BY SOIL-----	
ABd	16.4%
ABe	1.3%
ARc	0.0%
...	
RGe	0.3%

- 3.3. *Compare coefficients* is aimed for the comparison of two SWAT setups of the same watershed. If both a setup (*Load case*) and a reference setup (*Load comparison case*) are loaded then this menu selection compares the SWAT model coefficients of both setups and reports the non-matching ones.
- 3.4. *Data output* menu selections (Fig. 23 left) are aimed for the post processing of the SWAT modelling results; generally they are targeted at the implementation of the load, retention, riverine load and load apportionment

calculation methodics proposed in ELLE & PAIC (2012a). All menu selections prepare the output files and store them in the folder *Statistical*.

3.4.1. *Landuses* prepares a text file *landuse_statistics.txt* summarising the percentage of different land use areas for each subbasin of the SWAT setups of the modelling system (Table 3). This text file can be further used (joined by *CachID*) with the subbasin shape file.

Table 3. Contents of the *landuse_statistics.txt* file.

CachID	Agrc	Past	Frst	Urbn	Watr
480	0.1943	0	0.8057	0	0
486	0.47458	0.074263	0.24295	0.16363	0.044578
...					
680	0.75748	0.082399	0.14693	0.008064	0.005126

Table 4. Contents of the *area.txt* file.

cachID	A_WTSH	A_SUB	A_TRSB	A_AGRC	A_BCKG	A_URBA	A_HRU
480	4.98695	4.98695	0	0.841483	3.48943	0	4.33091
486	393.962	4.65225	0	2.57636	1.90853	0.209258	4.69414
...							
857	88.2235	88.2235	0	46.6711	22.8162	17.3041	86.7914

3.4.2. *Loads and Retention* prepares a list of files for the subbasin related integral load and retention parameters. The menu selection is designed for the use with the yearly outputs of the SWAT files. All these text files can be further used (joined by *CachID*) with the subbasin shape file. The respective files are:

3.4.2.1. *Basinloads.txt* – the annual substance (N-NO₃, N_{tot}, P-PO₄, P_{tot}) loads from the subbasin averaged over the calculation period and aggregated over the agricultural, forest, stormwater, transboundary, pointsource and alga sources, ELLE & PAIC (2012a).

3.4.2.2. *Reachloads.txt* – the annual substance (N-NO₃, N_{tot}, P-PO₄, P_{tot}) loads in the rivers flowing out of the subbasin averaged over the calculation period and separated as loads from the agricultural, forest, stormwater, transboundary, pointsource and alga sources, ELLE & PAIC (2012a).

3.4.2.3. *ReachQ.txt* – the annual discharge of the river leaving the subbasin averaged over the calculation period.

3.4.2.4. *Retention.txt* – the annual substance (N-NO₃, N_{tot}, P-PO₄, P_{tot}) retention in the reach of the subbasin separated as retention of pollution from the agricultural, forest, stormwater, transboundary, pointsource and alga sources.

3.4.2.5. *Areas.txt* – the areas of subbasin catchment, subbasin itself, its transboundary catchment, subbasin parts aggregated as agricultural, background and urban, and sum of HRU areas of the subbasin, see Table 4.

3.4.3. *LoadsByHRU* prepares the hydrological response unit level output – the annual loads of substances (N-NO₃, N_{tot}, P-PO₄, P_{tot}) from each HRU of the modelling system averaged over the calculation period. The menu selection requires the presence of the calculation results – yearly SWAT model outputs at the HRU level. The prepared files are *hruloads.shp*; the attribute database file *hruloads.dbf* includes the HRU characteristics (identifier of subbasin, land use, soil type, slope, area) and the loads from HRU, see Table 5.

Table 5. Contents of the *hruloads.dbf* file.

CACHID	LANDUSE	SOIL	SLOPE	AREA	NORG	NO3	NTOT	PORG	PO4	PTOT
480	AGRC	LVg	3.090	55.22760	0.578	1.941	2.518	0.070	0.044	0.114
480	AGRC	LVh	2.902	25.19298	0.298	2.483	2.781	0.036	0.027	0.063
480	FRSD	HSf	1.092	55.52508	0.000	11.475	11.475	0.000	0.080	0.080
480	FRSD	LVg	2.274	73.61971	0.000	0.642	0.642	0.000	0.033	0.033
480	FRST	HSf	0.923	88.78063	0.000	12.617	12.617	0.000	0.064	0.064
480	FRST	LVg	2.499	16.97654	0.000	0.641	0.641	0.000	0.026	0.026
480	FRSE	HSf	0.778	17.40736	0.000	12.049	12.049	0.000	0.043	0.043
480	WETF	HSf	1.183	81.25146	0.000	30.260	30.260	0.000	0.047	0.047
486	WPAS	HSs	3.072	10.77061	0.000	14.178	14.178	0.000	0.119	0.119
486	WPAS	LVg	3.828	10.77061	0.002	0.294	0.296	0.000	0.030	0.030
...										
857	URML	HSs	3.576	13.08994	0.266	8.566	8.832	0.049	0.255	0.304
857	URLD	LPk	13.107	10.06918	0.260	0.201	0.461	0.044	0.042	0.085

3.5. *View menu* (Fig. 23 right) includes two functions:

3.5.1. *Watershed overview* switches on/off the electronic map.

3.5.2. *Output.std* opens a text window for review of the SWAT standard output file of the loaded setup.

4. COMPARISON OF MODEL VS OBSERVATIONS

The basic functionality of visualisation and comparison of the modelled and observed data series are described in Section 3.2. There are two functional blocks for the advanced [statistical] postprocessing.

Calibration tab (Fig. 17, see p.3 of Section 3.2) is aimed for the selection of SWAT model results and the observation data series matching those calculation results. Button *Calibration statistics* performs the analysis of the differences between the modelled and observed data series and summarise this statistics in text window, see Fig. 24. The setup name, calibration and validation periods are included in this window along with the daily and monthly Nash-Suttcliff efficiency (*NSE*) and mass balance (*PBIAS*) for each of observed parameters, separately for calibration and validation periods.

VAR	CALIB			VALID		
	NSE		PBIAS	NSE		PBIAS
	daily	monthly	PBIAS	daily	monthly	PBIAS
Q	0.57	0.61	7.2%	0.72	0.86	-7.0%
N-NO3	0.64	0.46	51.8%			
N-NH4	-16.96	-1.67	52.4%			
N-Org	-1.05	-0.14	-40.6%			
P-PO4	0.08	-0.14	-53.7%			
P-Org	-9.55	-3.01	27.5%			
SS	-164.55	-14.77	320.6%			
BOD7	-54.40	-1.41	-37.3%			
DOX	0.50	0.43	40.2%			
QWQ	0.62	0.44	25.4%			

Figure 24. *Calibration statistics* text window.

The functional block *Statistics* of the control panel (See Figs. 2 and 25) is aimed at comparison of the data series selected for visualisation (in 1D graph panel). It considers the data series selected and processed in the functional block *Visualisation settings* (Fig.25, checkboxes *Concentrations*, *Monthly values*, *Normalised by area* may be applied). Fields *From* and *To* define the time period for analysis whilst radio buttons *Type* determine whether the statistics will be performed for average values (*Ave*), *Sum* of parameters (observation values and/or model results) or *Count* – amount of observations and/or model outputs.

Figure 25. *Statistics* functional block of the control panel.

Figure 26. *Annual and monthly statistics* graphical window.

Figure 27. *Correlations* graphical window.

Button *Statistics* invokes a graphical window (Fig. 26). The upper part of the window contains the annual and monthly statistics of the selected (observed or modelled) parameters – average values, sums or number of data items in the series. The lower part of the graphical window contains the monthly time graphs of these selected parameters. The right part of the window is aimed for the formatting of the visualisation. Its functionality is the same as of *Visualisation settings* functional block – see description in Section 3.2.

Button *Correlations* invokes a graphical window (Fig. 27) for correlation analysis. In the right panel of the window user may choose two of selected parameters for a visualisation along the *X* and *Y* axis by radio buttons. The 1D graph – one selected parameter vs. another is displayed in the central part of the graphical window. The left part of the graphical window contains the correlation analysis (tables) of all considered time series. The respective tables include (1) Nash-Suttcliff efficiencies (*NSE*) of the pairs of parameter time series, (2) the difference of time integrals or mass balance (*PBIAS*, in %), (3) coefficients of determination (*R2*) of the pairs of parameter time series, (4) average values (*AVE*) of the parameters and (5) number of entries (*COUNT*) in the time series.

5. SWAT PARAMETERS AND CALCULATIONS

The dialogue *Show/Edit SWAT variables* (Fig. 28) is invoked by the pull-down menu selection *Actions*→*Edit SWAT variables*. This menu selection allows for the handling of the SWAT parameters of the loaded SWAT setup.

The left part of the dialogue window contains the list of the SWAT variables while the right part – the control panel. The following functionality is available:

Figure 28. *Show/Edit SWAT variables* dialogue window.

1. The central part of the control panel contains a block of checkboxes. Each checkbox contains a name of SWAT variable block (or variable types). The SWAT variables are listed in the left part of the dialogue window according to the status of checkboxes after pressing button *Redraw variables*. User may use buttons – pictograms to select / unselect all checkboxes.
2. The button *Save project* saves the actual set of SWAT variables into SWAT data files of loaded setup folder (*TxtInOut* is default folder).
3. The button *Run SWAT2005* copies the SWAT executable file *SWAT2009_paic.exe* to the appropriate setup folder and runs the SWAT model on the loaded SWAT setup. The progress dialogue (Fig. 29) is displayed during the calculations. Note that SWAT uses the data files written in the respective SWAT folder of particular setup – therefore user must save the changes made in SWAT parameters before they have effect on calculations.
4. The block of radio buttons *Sort by* determines the sequence of SWAT variables in the left part of the dialogue window. Each variable is named as *type.name* in SWAT. *None* assumes no sorting and the variables appears as in SWAT files. *Variable name* assumes alphabetic sorting of variables within the unsorted list of the variable blocks (types). *Variable name + Vartypename*

assumes alphabetic sorting of both the variable blocks and the variables within these blocks.

Figure 29. Progress output window during the SWAT calculations.

Figure 30. Non-aggregated SWAT variable list.

5. The appearance of the SWAT variable list is controlled by the radio buttons and checkboxes in the *Aggregation* block of the control panel.
 - a. Radiobutton *None* assumes no aggregation of variables (see Figs. 28, 30). Columns of the variable list contain (1) *Variable* - variable type and name, (2) *Place* – HRU number, subbasin number, land use and soil type, and (3) *Value*.
 - b. Radiobutton *Domain* assumes aggregation of variables over the catchment (see Figs. 31, 32). The columns of the variable list contain (1) *Variable* – variable type and name, (2) *Count* – number of

aggregated values, (3) average, minimum and maximum of the aggregated values.

Variable	Count	AveValue	MinValue	MaxValue
SOL.SOL_ZMX	582	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
SOL.ANION_EXCL	582	0.500	0.500	0.500
SOL.SOL_CRK	582	0.500	0.500	0.500
SOL.SOL_Z(1)	582	300.0000	300.0000	300.0000
SOL.SOL_Z(2)	582	1000.0000	1000.0000	1000.0000
SOL.SOL_BD(1)	582	1.4886	1.2600	1.7300
SOL.SOL_BD(2)	582	1.4504	1.3000	1.7100
SOL.SOL_AWC(1)	582	0.1560	0.0236	0.2360

Figure 31. Domain aggregated SWAT variable list.

Variable	Count	AveValue	MinValue	MaxValue
SOL.SOL_ZMX	582	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
SOL.ANION_EXCL	582	0.500	0.500	0.500
SOL.SOL_CRK	582	0.500	0.500	0.500
SOL.SOL_Z	1164	650.0000	300.0000	1000.0000
SOL.SOL_BD	1164	1.4666	1.2600	1.7300
SOL.SOL_AWC	1164	0.1630	0.0236	0.2360
SOL.SOL_K	1164	111.9905	12.0000	300.0000
SOL.SOL_CBN	1164	3.8327	0.2100	39.4000

Figure 32. Domain and array aggregated SWAT variable list.

Variable	Place	C..	AveValue	MinValue	MaxValue
SOL.SOL_ZMX	1=1:URML	2	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
SOL.SOL_ZMX	2=1:AGRC	13	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
SOL.SOL_ZMX	3=1:WPAS	11	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
SOL.SOL_ZMX	4=1:FRST	9	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
SOL.SOL_ZMX	5=1:FRSE	2	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
SOL.SOL_ZMX	6=1:FRSD	8	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
SOL.SOL_ZMX	7=1:WETF	1	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00
SOL.SOL_ZMX	8=1:WATR	1	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00

Figure 33. Soil type aggregated SWAT variable list.

- i. User may additionally *Aggregate arrays*, i.e. all elements of the SWAT array variables (Fig. 32) by the respective checkbox.
- ii. If the *HRU aggregation* checkboxes (*Subbasin*, *LandUse* or *Soil*, see Fig. 19) of the *Load settings* group are applied during the load of the SWAT setup (see Section 3.3, p.1) then user may apply checkbox *Use HRU aggregation* to aggregate the

HRU with that selected characteristics – subbasin, soil (example in Fig. 33) or land use.

- c. Radiobutton *Domain+Value* assumes aggregation of variables with the same value over the catchment (see Fig. 34). The columns of the variable list contain (1) *Variable* – variable type and name, (2) *Count* – number of aggregated values, (3) *Value*.

Figure 34. List of domain aggregated SWAT variables of different values.

Figure 35. The dialogue of editing SWAT parameter values.

- 6. The editing of the values of SWAT variables of the loaded setup is possible by double mouseclick in the list of parameters. The dialogue window (Fig. 35) is invoked. The number of the affected variables is displayed in the field *Count*, as well as their *MinValue* and *Maxvalue*. The simultaneous editing of multiple parameters is possible depending on the aggregation level of the list – see p.5 above. User may enter the new parameter *Value* and perform the editing operation by one of two methods (radiobuttons *Type*):

- a. *Value* – the old parameter value(s) will be replaced by the new one(s).

- b. *Relative* – the new parameter value(s) will be calculated from the old one(s) according to formula in Fig. 35.

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